

Energy balance analysis of Biomass Gasification and Utilization of Syn Gas using Aspen Plus.

Report submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of
B.Tech.

In
Chemical Engineering
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Prof. Vinita Khandegar

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Certificate

This is to certify that the project report titled “Energy balance analysis of Biomass Gasification and Utilization of Syn Gas using Aspen Plus” submitted to University School of Chemical Technology, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, Delhi.in fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Batchelor of Engineering in Chemical Engineering embodies the original research work carried out by Mr. Pravind Kumar Thakur under the supervision of Prof. Vinita Khandegar. This work has not been submitted in part or full for any degree or diploma to this or any other University.

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Declaration

I hereby declare that the project title “Energy balance analysis of Biomass Gasification and Utilization of Syn Gas using Aspen Plus” is an authentic record of the research work conducted by me and is free from any falsification and plagiarism. This work was carried out under the supervision of Prof. Vinita Khandegar at University School of Chemical Technology, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha university, New Delhi. I assume full responsibility for any disputes that may arise from the content of my research work.

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Abstract

I derived inspiration for this project from my previous internship experiences, particularly my time at Adani Electricity in 2021, where I gained insights into the operations of large-scale industries. Additionally, my tenure at Topsoe in 2023 provided me with a deep understanding of process engineering principles and expertise in simulation methodologies. This project report presents a comprehensive exploration of energy balance analysis concerning biomass gasification and the utilization of synthesis gas (syngas) using Aspen Plus software. Undertaken as a major project, it was conducted within the academic realm under the guidance of Prof. Vineeta Khandegar leveraging the resources and expertise available.

In the evolving energy landscape, the focus on sustainable solutions has heightened the importance of understanding biomass gasification and syngas utilization. These processes offer significant potential for renewable energy generation and reducing carbon emissions.

The report begins with an overview of the critical roles played by biomass gasification and syngas utilization in achieving sustainability goals within the energy sector. It delineates the project's objectives, which include bridging theoretical concepts with practical applications and gaining a profound understanding of energy balance analysis in biomass conversion processes.

Methodologies employed encompass literature review, advanced computational simulations using Aspen Plus, and active engagement in project development. The report underscores the collaborative nature of the project, where interactions with experts and peers facilitated a deeper comprehension of the subject matter.

By analyzing energy balance within the biomass gasification process and exploring various pathways for syngas utilization, this project contributes valuable insights to the field of renewable energy research. It underscores the significance of optimizing energy efficiency and sustainability in biomass conversion technologies.

Overall, this project serves as a significant contribution to advancing knowledge in biomass utilization and underscores the potential of syngas as a renewable energy resource.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Energy is the primitive basis of the modern world's growth and for meeting life's daily needs. Energy plays a pivotal role in the progress of developing nations and in bringing sustainability to the developed nations. Hence naturally the demand for this source is increased and it plays a major role in deciding the economy of various nations.

Conventional energy resources are rapidly depleting with large demand of gap between usage and requirement. Conversion of biomass resources to energy plays an important role in reducing this gap. Biomass energy conversion system constitutes generation of various byproducts for different usage systems. The energy conversion from the biomass to electricity with thermal power thermal energy generated by the process can be used in different processes in industries.

1.1. Biomass:

Biomass is one of the main sources for energy generation in the renewable energy sector because of its enormous supply in regard to fuel that can be used for generation of energy. Various technologies are employed for the process of conversion from wastes to useful energy by combustion to continuously progressing gasification, digestion and others. These techniques are actively taking part in converting the biomass feedstock (collectively wastes and feed from various plant derivatives) to useful energy needed by industries and manhood.

Biomass feedstocks range from agricultural wastes, agricultural residues, wastes from various process industries, energy crops and algae. Cultivation of energy crops is at a very large scale in various developing countries.

Figure 1.1 Gasification Path

The chemical energy of the biomass feedstock was converted into electricity or heat by the process of combustion or gasification. Biofuels was compared as the best replacement for conventional fossil fuel for energy generation and as a transportation fuel. This will also reduce the GHG emissions to the atmosphere by using various fossil fuels.

1.2. Gasification of Biomass

Energy conversion from front biomass feedstock to gasification comprises of different phases. They are:

- Pyrolysis
- Combustion
- Gas phase reactions

In pyrolysis thermochemical conversion of the biomass feed stock takes place in the absence of oxygen. The resultant products from pyrolysis are charcoal and gases including methane, Carbon mono-oxide, Carbon di-oxide and Hydrogen. The stream is then processed by gasification agent to convert the product of pyrolysis to syn gas. Syn gas then can be utilized in different systems to generate the heat and power.

Syn gas has char and other constituents, which will be removed by using scrubber. Char also removed from the syngas before the process of energy generation.

Syn gas produced through gasification process has successively been used in various utility systems for energy generation. Fluidized bed gasification was classified according to superficial velocity of gases through fluidized bed. The flow velocity of the Bubbling bed will be lesser than the superficial velocity of the column. But in fluidized bed gasification, velocity of gasification agent will be higher than the superficial velocity. Fluidized bed gasifiers have low residence time reactivity of char is low. Circulating bed has higher gas velocity due to the in the entrainment of bed material on gasification medium. This will be circulated back to the reactor for high carbon conversion.

Figure 1.2: Gasification Flow Diagram

1.3. Utilization System

Utilization of syn gas generated by gasification in industries is done through continuous heat and power techniques. Small scale use utilizes gas engines for useful energy conversion. Continuous heat and power systems utilize the heat of gases to expand in gas turbine or by rising steam turbine with conversion of heat value through heat transfer equipment. Heat in the form of steam is also generated in this system.

Various systems have been utilized in the process of energy conversion from syn gas. Some of the systems process of energy conversion are Closed cycle gas turbine, Gas Engine and Solid oxide fuel cell system. Waste heat from gas turbines will pass through waste heat recovery systems to generate energy through gas turbines.

By using the back pressure turbine, we can generate steam at required pressures for processing heat. Steam turbines with the extraction at different pressures can also be used in this process. This also increases the efficiency of the steam turbine.

Various utilization system is:

- Continuous heat and power
- Direct Electric conversion system

1.3.1. Continuous Heat and Power

Various process industries use continuous heat and power system for fulfilling their energy needs for process and their utilities. This system will fulfill the industry need of both thermal and electrical energy. It has been classified according to the usage.

- Power generation through gas turbine and process heating application
- Combined cycle power generation through gas turbines and steam turbines with process heating applications

Industries majorly use the latter system than the former as the losses through the former system is more. Because exhaust gases carry away larger amount of heat from the system. The former also affect the environment on a larger scale due to passing the exhaust gases at much higher temperatures.

Whereas in later system the efficiency has been boosted with increased energy usage in gas turbine additionally generation of energy by steam turbine.

The temperature of the exhaust gases must be maintained at minimum to reduce the emissions to the environment and also to utilize the heat from flue gas to maximum extent for increase the efficiency.

1.3.2. Direct Electric Conversion System

Direct electric conversion system is majorly unfamiliar Magneto Hydro Dynamic systems (MHD) which utilizes the gases from the process will the expand in MHD turbine. Electricity is directly produced in the systems by magnetic action.

1.4. Drying of Biomass

A major problem concerning biomass energy conversion system is losses due to the moisture in fuel. This reduces the efficiency of combustion and the efficiency of boiler. Emissions from combustion of wet biomass increase the temperature of the gases on the stack. This can be reduced by utilizing the energy from flue gas to dry the fuel. This increases the efficiency of combustion, boiler and reduces the net air emissions to environment. Dryer consumes energy for the purpose of heating and evaporation of the fuel's moisture content which will reduce the residual moisture of the feed.

1.5. Objectives

The objectives of the project are,

- Energy balance of syngas utilization on downstream.
- Analysis of the thermodynamic efficiency of utilization system on downstream for the different models.
- Comparing the utilization system with the direct biomass combustion System.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1. Biomass Resources

A report made by [8] says, total biomass resources in the world is 1800 billion tons and Energy from various feed stocks on earth will account to 33000 EJ which is 80 times more than the total annual energy consumption by world. Biomass resources are diverse, including resources from forests and oceans. Energy available from different. systems get varied according to types of resources. Biomass resources has been classified according to,

- Biomass from agricultural residues
- Biomass from waste

As per the sugar technologist association of India [2], Variety of by products has been available from various industries that can be utilized in the energy conversion. The total energy from the biomass resource is approximately 128 EJ, in that the agricultural biomass amounts to 48 EJ with livestock biomass of 43 EJ followed by forestry biomass amounts to about 37 EJ.

* t/t - waste generated with respect to tons of useful crop Biomass feedstock constitute:

Biomass Species	Waste Production Rate (t/t)	Energy conversion co-efficient (GJ/t)
Wheat	1.3	17.5
Sugarcane Residue	0.28	17.33
Rice	1.4	16.31
Maize (Corn)	1	17.7
Roots and Tubers	0.4	6

Table 2.1: Biomass Feedstock energy Co-efficient [2]

2.2. Global Sugar Cane Processing Industry

As per the Sugar technologist association of India [2], World production of sugar has been controlled by Brazil, India, and China. It needs a water requirement of 1.2 - 1.6 m/year and the maturing period is about 9 - 14 months. Food and Market exchange states that a sugar mill produce with a crushing capacity of 3000 TCD (Tons of Cane per day) will produce varied products of sugar, molasses and energy. It produces sugar at a rate of 345 tons of sugar, with byproducts of 3 tons of yeast, alcohol from molasses from at a rate of 6000 liters with potash fertilizer at range of 15 tons, mud fertilizer ranges about 150 tons, pulp of about 25 tons which can be used for production of paper and electricity of about 240 MWh. As per [8], Bagasse is the final residue of sugarcane which is a fibrous stalk. There will be better bagasse yield over the period of maturity of cane end also by efficient of crushing. Remains of sugar onto the cane affect the efficiency of power generation on the power generation system.

2.3. Potential of Bagasse

According to [2], the remains from sugar was used in the process of energy generation. Paper was produced from pulp that remained during the processing of cane. India is processing about 40 MMT of bagasse around the year. With the minimal use of pulp for paper production the remaining is available for energy conversion. There are about 500 sugar cane industries in India on which majority of industries are being located around Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Punjab in North India, Gujarat, and Maharashtra in Western part of India. In southern part of India, the sugar cane processing industries are being located

at Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, and Karnataka. As per the report made by [9], volume of the gas produced by the bagasse gasification is much lesser than the direct combustion. The gas production is not affected by any means of feed characteristics as the feed is uniform bagasse and hence it doesn't affect the design of gasifier due to non-uniform feed. CFB gasifier is best suited for gas production as there is a higher volumetric capacity of the gasifier. This increases the efficiency of carbon conversion. Since the flexibility of the gasifier is higher if CFB is incorporated onto the system, thereby the efficiency of the gas conversion system is higher. As the Circulating fluidized bed has been used the volumetric capacity of the gasifier can be easily controlled.

2.4. Bagasse Gasification

Report made by [16], cites industries incorporate direct combustion for the energy conversion from bagasse, which has very lesser thermodynamic efficiency than gasification. As most of the sugar cane industry currently has back pressure turbine for the energy production process, the thermodynamic efficiency of the system was reduced much lesser.

Saroj Mishra reported the use of gasification will increase the efficiency of energy conversion. Net thermal efficiency of the gasification system is around 40 - 45 %. Gasification process also has an increased opportunity because the sugar industry produces about 150 tons of press mud/ day on the plant during the process of sugar production. This can be utilized apart from the energy conversion of bagasse gasification separately. As the bagasse gasification has needs lesser volumetric capacities, this can be utilized in small and large mills irrespectively. This will be the major advantage of gasification compared to combustion technique which has a higher loss in case at smaller one.

2.5. Energy Utilization from Syngas

Energy from the syn gas has been utilized by various systems using the principles of Brayton cycle and Rankine cycle. While the Brayton cycle utilizes the gas utilization in the gas turbine, whereas the Rankine cycle utilizes the waste heat to energy in the Heat recovery steam generation systems for energy conversion. Continuous heat and power systems has been the major principle for converting gas to useful energy in the form of heat and electricity. Various Continuous heat and power utilization systems are, [10]

- Gas Turbine
- Gas Engine
- Solid oxide fuel cell

2.5.1. Rankine Cycle

In the Rankine cycle the heat from the flue gas has been transferred to the water thereby the conversion of water to steam takes place at a higher pressure.

- 1-2 Isentropic pump work
- 2-3 Constant pressure heat addition
- 3-4 Isentropic Turbine work
- 4-1 Constant pressure heat rejection

Figure 2.1. Rankine Cycle

On explaining Rankine cycle R S Khurmi states that [14], In 1-2 feed pump pumps water from condenser to boiler which is operating at a higher-pressure fluid needs to be in liquid state for this operation. At 2-3 heat was transferred to water at a constant pressure for the conversion of water onto steam. And on 3-4 steam has been expanded in the turbine to generate work. By rejecting the heat on the condenser steam has been condensed onto the water.

2.5.2. Brayton Cycle

Instead of water in Rankine cycle air has been used as a working fluid in the system.

1-2 Isentropic compression

2-3 Constant pressure heat addition

3-4 Isentropic expansion in Gas turbine

4-1 Constant pressure heat rejection

Figure 2.2. Brayton Cycle

On explaining Rankine Cycle R.S Khurmi states that [14], in 1-2 working fluid has been compressed to the highest pressure and then it has been heated at constant temperatures to the higher temperatures. Then by expanding in the gas turbine heat has been rejected to the atmosphere as flue gas. The downstream of syn gas utilization through the Brayton cycle can be coupled with the heat recovery system.

2.6. Combined Cycle Gas Turbine

According to Richard Toonsen [18], Combined cycle utilizes both Rankine cycle and Brayton cycles on the system. This has been done by syngas combustion according to the Brayton cycle. The studies based on Jayakumar [11], says the gas from petcoke gasification has efficiency higher than expansion of steam in the steam turbine by combustion process. Efficiency also relates to the increase in the cost of the gasification system. But this can be recovered faster than the Combustion system models because of higher efficiency. The efficiency of the gasification process is 10% more than the combustion model of expansion.

According to R Bachman [3], the combined cycle systems have been majorly employed in the gas turbine cycle system. In this model heat carried away by the gases plays a major role because the cooling gases quantity increases if the heat produced on the combustion is more.

Jayakumar [11] reported that auxiliary power consumption on combined cycle is more than the steam turbine utilization due to increase in the work required by the compressor for compressing the inlet air for combustion in combustion chamber. When the inlet temperature of the gas gets reduced, work required by compressor is considerably reduced.

R S Khurmi states that [14], inter-cooling and reheat can be preferred in gas turbine systems. This will increase the efficiency of the system. The requirement for the combustion of syngas will be reduced. The Brayton cycle produces a higher efficiency than the Rankine cycle, since the cycle is majorly dependent upon heating the working fluids to higher temperatures. Adiabatic compressor efficiency plays a major role in the system. Because of the increase in adiabatic compressor efficiency, overall cycle efficiency of the system will get increased due to the reduced compressor losses. This will increase the temperature of air towards the combustion chamber stream.

According to Roelf Bachman [3], the importance of the air passed for the compressor is based on the complete combustion in Combustion chamber. Gases from combustion chamber were allowed to expand in the gas turbine. The maximum temperature of the gas turbine operation should be less than 1550°C, hence the cooling air has been allowed to reduce the operational temperature of the gas turbine. To maintain this, a greater amount of cooling air was allowed into the turbine.

Wayne Doherty reported [4], At low temperatures of operation more amount of fuel is inlet into the system to maintain the higher power generation by the gas turbine. The efficiency of the system has been about 40 - 45%. Introducing a fuel dryer on to the system will reduce the efficiency of the cycle.

Figure 2.3. Combined Cycle

2.7. Utilization System through Gas Engine

Gregorio reported [1], syn gas utilization system through the gas engine of reciprocating type which depends on the quality of the fuel input to the gas engine. The exit of the gas engine has been used in the process heating of the fuel and water for gasification.

As per C. Zygarlicke [19], gas engine system needs clean gas without any impurities like acids, tars and dust from the gasification process. Gas with these particles will cause wear and tear on engine surface. The combustion parameters of syn gas engines are different from other fuel combusted in gas engines. Compression ignition (CI) mode of combustion is preferred over the Spark Ignition (SI) engine for syn gas utilization systems. SI engines won't operate with higher efficiency at changing pressure ratios due to improper mixing of the gases.

Sridhar reports [6], the emissions on the combustion of syn gas are more than the other utilization system. Since combustion is due to the release of unburnt carbon on the exhaust of system. Efficiency of the syn gas combustion produces comparatively less efficiency than the gasoline fuel burning in the system. Process heat systems have been extended to process air heating and for processing steam generation for gasification.

Figure 2.4. Schematic of combined cycle using gas turbine (Brayton cycle) and steam turbine (Rankine cycle) [Langston]

2.8. Solid Oxide Fuel Cell

Wayne Doherty [4], explains that thermochemical action takes place in fuel cells to generate heat and electricity from syngas. Unburnt syngas combustion gets reduced in fuel cell which increases the efficiency of combustion.

Raido Huberg explains [7] that SOFC is made up of Yttria - Stabilized Zirconia is a non - porous metal oxide with solid electrolyte acts as a conductor of oxygen. O^{2-} will act as the carrier of charge between anode and cathode. The reactions in the anode and cathode are as follows,

Vincenzo Liso states that [12], working of the SOFC is similar to inter - cooling in the gas turbine wherein the gas flowing out will increase the temperature of compressed air. In SOFC instead of increasing the temperature of air, syngas is passed through the fuel cell to produce an additional power on the systems. Outlet from SOFC is allowed to expand in gas turbine to produce additional power.

Richard Toonsen reports [18], irrespective of their nature of fuel energy can generated through Fuel Cell. Some of the fuels used in fuel tell are methanol, syn gas through biomass gasification, natural gas, kerosene, and coal because of its higher operating temperatures.

Wayne Doherty states that [4], Solid oxide fuel cell has been integrated with the gas turbines is currently manufactured by Siemen’s Electric. Preheating of air increases the operational temperature of fuel cells. Reduction in fuel cells. Air and steam have been produced by using various heat transfer equipment. Reaction in the fuel cell starts when it approaches the walls of fuel cell.

Figure 2.5. SOFC Flow Diagram

According to Vincencio Liso [12], various factor affecting the property of the fuel cell model is,

- Utilization factor
- Current density
- Steam to Carbon ratio.

The utilization factor defines the amount of syngas utilized in the system for conversion in fuel cell. Oxygen is used as conductor in fuel cells. With decrease in utilization factor, voltage produced in fuel cell is also get reduced. Reactions taking place in preformer has been responsible for conversion of syn gas components to hydrogen rich stream.

Figure 2.6. Fuel Cell Model

Reduced current density in fuel cells increases voltage losses on cells. This results in a reduction of power produced through the fuel cell. Parasitic losses and energy input to fuel cell (by compressors and fuel) get with increased air consumption on fuel cell.

The need of the preforming in fuel cell reported by Vincenzo Liso as [12],

- To heat the mixture of depleted and fuel towards on to the fuel cell.
- For partial conversion of methane on the to hydrogen.
- Water gas shift reaction on the system.

Increasing of STCR (Steam to Carbon Ratio) decrease in mole fraction Of H₂ and CO with increase of CO₂ and H₂O ratio on the fuel cell, thus improves the combustion efficiency and stock performance of the solid oxide fuel cell and gas turbine. Combusted gas is then allowed to pass through. This process has been come under the continuous heat and power system wherein the syn gas has been allowed to pass through gas turbine. Campanari states [15] that, working temperature of the fuel cell is around 600 - 1000°C due to material constraints.

High temperatures are maintained in the fuel cell to increase the conductivity of the fuel cell. When operating under lower temperatures the solid electrolyte is not able to conduct the oxygen through the fuel cell. Fuel cell produces energy in Direct current (DC), by using inverter it converts into AC.

Different Operational parameters discussed are:

- **Operating at part loads:**

Vincenzo Liso [12], shows that fuel cells operate at higher efficiency during part loads with in- crease in voltage. Increase in voltage is due to maintaining stack temperatures at outlet of fuel cell. Because of the reduction in the load on the system, voltage along the cell decreases with an increase in the voltage of the cell and thereby increase of electrical efficiency.

- **Full load Operations:**

Vilencio Lizo [12], at full load operation system voltage get increased to higher extent because of increase in temperature of gases. This directly increases the voltage on full operation.

Wayne Doherty [4], shows that the Power to the heat ratio has been comparatively increased by about 12% with inclusion of Solid Oxide fuel cell on system.

2.9. Drying of Biomass

R Bachman [3] states that biomass feed stocks of all kinds have moisture content. Combustion efficiency in boilers decreased considerably. Whereas gasification efficiency does not affect considerably. The drying of feed stock depends on the type of gasifier used for gasification and the amount of tars generated during gasification. In Fluidized bed and Updraft gasifier moisture content about 65 % and 80% can be accommodated.

Drying biomass increases the LHV of the feed stock and also the efficiency of the gasification. The chemical exergy of the biomass feedstock has been increased with the chemical exergies on H₂ and CO.

Jayakumar reports [11] that, increase in moisture content will decrease the efficiency of gasification. So, the fuel is sent to the drying system and then to the gasification system. Drying of feedstock can include the system if the gasification temperature is beyond the carbon - boundary temperature of biomass feedstock. Efficiency of the drying majorly depends on the dryer temperature. Hence drying becomes essential for the system. Hence the heat from the flue gas will be utilized for the process of drying.

Anne Jayanthi reports that moisture content in bagasse was about 35%-55% after crushing of the sugar cane in the industry. Total generation in bagasse is around 25-30% of cane crushed in the industry. The heating value of the bagasse is around 9000 KJ/kg. By drying the heating value of bagasse also increases the energy generation from the system.

Emissions and air requirement for combustion of feedstock reduced by the process of drying. Air drying is the best option for the drying of feedstock as it has the best energy efficiency compared to other drying processes. Bagasse feedstock get burnt when the fuel is dried beyond carbon-boundary temperature by using fine gas drying temperature at the exit of system get reduced.

Various sources are being used for the drying of biomass feedstock in industries. Steam has higher exergetic losses in the process of drying. But the flue gas and air-drying system will produce a higher efficiency than the steam drying systems.

2.10. Thermodynamic Efficiency of different systems

Roelf Bachman states [3] that, different systems have been employed for the utilization of syn gas depends on the end gas application needed by the users.

2.10.1. Gas Turbine System

Valencio Lizo states [12] that the gas turbine energy conversion system is the most efficient one and it is suitable for both the large and small scales.

Jaykumar reports [11] that, Gas needs to be cleaner without any tar content when it has expanded in the gas turbine. Because the tar content will affect the operation of turbine. Pressure and temperature losses in cleaning gases will reduce the temperature of gases inlet to the utilization system. This will reduce the combustion efficiency of the CC. Gas cleaning operations will increase the auxiliary work needed by the system R.S Khurmi suggests [14] that, inter-cooling will increase the temperature of air inlet to the combustion chamber which utilize heat from hot gas from outlet of gas turbine.

2.10.2. Gas Engine system

Mukund Sridhar stated that [5], gas engine needs similar to the gas turbine as the tar content is allowed in a minimal level. Cleaning of syn gas from the outlet of gasifier is essential to run the prime mover of gas engine. Selecting gas engine oil for syn gas fuel mainly depends on tar content in syn gas. Gas engine is much higher efficient and most economical at smaller sizes and scale. M Santonastasi reports that [1], With increase in capacities, size of the engine gets increased. But this system has very easy start-up compared to the gas turbine systems. But majorly gas engine systems have been restricted to small-scale electricity production.

2.10.3. Solid Oxide Fuel Cell System

Raido Huberg reports that [7], solid oxide fuel cell uses bottoming cycle for power generation. This cycle produces a higher efficiency corresponds to the higher work with addition of work done through the Gas turbine combined cycle. Fuel cells need high-cost material for its manufacturing hence the cost of the solid oxide fuel cell model will cost more than the actual combined cycle system of gas engine, gas turbine and other continuous heat and power application systems. The plant operating with SOFC is producing higher efficiency than the gas engine system, since it has a continuous heat and power application with the SOFC model of power generation.

2.10.4. Combustion system

Jayakumar explains that [11], combustion system has been majorly depending on the maximum temperature of the boiler tubes used for the combustion systems. Since it has air minimum cost of buildup and lesser period for the finishing, it seems more favorable. But the scale formation is higher in the line of the water arid steam along the combustion surface which reduce the system efficiency on long run. The limiting size of the boiler plays a major role in this system which needs a bigger if a higher power generation system is needed. Combustion and electricity conversion efficiency is lower compared to gasification.

Energy Conversion Device	Next Electrical Efficiency
Steam turbine	10-20%
Gas turbine	15-25%
Externally fired gas turbine	10-20%
Gas engine	13-28%

Figure 2.2. Comparison between different systems.

Chapter 3

Theoretical Development

3.1. Process Description

Syn gas generated from the gasification is allowed to pass through utilization system for energy conversion. Various utilization systems used for the energy conversion analyzed in this project are Closed cycle gas turbine, Gas Engine and Solid oxide fuel cell. The utilization system is modelled to extract the maximum heat from input fed onto the system.

3.2. Product Gas Utilization by Closed cycle Gas Turbine

Syn gas is fed into the utilization system at a temperature of 400°. Gas fed into utilization system doesn't have any tar content onto it. After combustion with air, mixture is allowed to expand in gas turbine. The inlet temperature of the gas turbine is maintained at or below 1500° C. Air is compressed from ambient conditions on compressor, pressure ratio of 9 is maintained in compressor. Combusted gas is expanded in Gas turbine to lower pressure to extract maximum amount of work from it. By waste heat recovery system, steam is generated to expand in steam turbine.

3.2.1. Energy in Producer Gas

Energy in the producer gas is calculated by calculating heat available on fuel and by the sensible heat in fuel. The heat on the fuel is the low heating value of the gas and the sensible heat is the heat taken away by the gas on the cooling of the gas on the system.

$$E_{syn} = m_{syn} * LHV_{syn} + C_{pi} * dT$$

E_{syn} : Energy in Syngas in KW

M_{syn} : Mass of Syngas flow into system

LHV_{syn} : Low heating value of syngas

3.2.2. Energy in Air

Air has been sent to the system to combust the syngas on the combustion chamber to produce energy. The gas needs to be sent inside the compressor at very low temperature which makes the compressor need less power.

$$E_{air} = m_{air} * C_{pair} * (T_{air} - T_{ref})$$

E_{air} : Energy in KW

C_{pair} : Specific heat capacity of air at constant pressure in KJ/kg

T_{air} : Temperature of air inlet to the system in K

T_{ref} : Reference temperature taken for consideration in K

3.3. Energy Output

3.3.1. Energy produced in the Gas Turbine

The combusted gas has been expanded to produce energy. The expanded gases have then been utilized in for the process heat generation.

$$\text{Work}_{produced} = \text{Enthalpy}_{of_gas_at_inlet} - \text{Enthalpy}_{of_gas_at_outlet}$$

3.3.2. Energy utilized for HRSG.

The total utilized by the heat recovery steam generation system is,

Heat utilized by the HRSG system = H1 + H2 + H3 + H4

$$\text{Total_heat_available_in_the_flue_gas_system} = m_{flue} * C_{pair} * (T_{flue} - 378)$$

M_{flue} : Mass of fluid in kg/hr

C_{pair} : Specific heat capacity of air at constant pressure in KJ/kg.

T_{flue} : Flue gas temperature in K.

3.3.3. Heat Load in Economizer

The economiser operating temperature will be 150°C.

$$\text{Total_heat_available_or_used_by_economiser } H_1 = (m_f * (hf_0 - hf_1))/3600$$

H1: Heat load in economizer

Mf: mass of fluid in kg/hr

Hf0: Enthalpy of water at outlet of economizer

Hf1: Enthalpy of hot water at inlet of economizer

3.3.4. Heat Load in Boiler

The economizer operating temperature will be 400°C which is heating water from 150°C.

$$\text{Total_heat_available_in_the_boiler } H_2 = m_f * (h_{fg} - h_f)/3600$$

H2: Heat load in boiler

Mf: mass of fluid in kg/hr

Hfg: enthalpy of water stream mixture before the entry of boiler hf – enthalpy of water before the entry of boiler.

3.3.5. Heat Load in Super Heater

The super heater has been operating at 40 bar @ 400°C.

$$\text{Total_heat_available_in_the_super_heater} = (m_f * (h_s - h_g))/3600$$

Mf: mass of fluid in Kg/hr.

Hs: Enthalpy of super-heated steam in KJ/hr.

Hg: Enthalpy of dry stream in KJ/kg.

3.3.6. Heat lost in the condensate.

The condensate has been operated under 0.8 bar@55°C.

$$\text{Heat_in_condensate_hc} = h_f + h_{fg} \text{ KJ/kg.}$$

Hc: Enthalpy of condensate in KJ/kg.

Hf: Enthalpy of water entering the condensate in KJ/kg.

Hfg: Enthalpy of water stream mixture entering the condensate in KJ/kg.

3.3.7. Work produced by the Steam Turbine

$$\text{Work_produced_by_the_steam_turbine} = (m_f * (h_s - h_c))/3600$$

Mf: mass of fluid in kg/hr.

Hs: Enthalpy of super-heated steam in KJ/kg.

Hc: Enthalpy of condensate in KJ/kg.

3.4. Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Model

Solid oxide fuel cell model calculation depends on the partial pressure, operational temperature and consumption of hydrogen in the solid oxide fuel. Solid oxide fuel cell model mainly depends on hydrogen consumption in reaction. The operational temperature of the fuel cell is around 900°C which is the main constraint of fuel cell.

3.4.1. Hydrogen consumption in system

$$\text{Total_hydrogen_in_syn_gas} = n_{H2syngas} + I(n_{COsyngas}) + 4 * (n_{CH4syngas})$$

n_{H2syngas}: number of hydrogen molecules in syngas.

n_{COsyngas}: number of carbon mono-oxide molecules in syngas.

n_{CH4syngas}: number of methane molecules in syngas.

Utilization factor (U_f) of solid oxide is,

$$U_f = n_{H2consumed}/n_{Hin}$$

$$\text{Oxygen_consumed_nO2consumed} = 0.5n_{H2consumed}$$

n_{H2consumed}: Total hydrogen consumed by solid oxide fuel cell

n_{Hin}: Hydrogen consumed by fuel cell.

n_{O2consumed}: Oxygen consumed by fuel cell.

Split ratio for the cathode on to the cell:

$$\text{Split_ratio_O}_{2split} = n_{O2consumed}/n_{O2in}$$

Oxygen is diverted on to cathode for a required level needed for combustion in anode. The air sent inside the system is maintained below temperature of the combustion. Hence the heat added, and the temperature maintained in the system will play a major role in the system.

3.4.2. Voltage Calculation

Voltage calculation of the system has been done by calculating the Nernst equation with accommodating the losses of ohmic, concentration and activation losses. Formula for calculating the Nernst voltage of system is:

$$V_N = (\Delta G_f / 2F) + (R_g * T_{avg} / 2F) * \ln (P_{H_2} P_{O_2}^{0.5} / P_{H_2O})$$

V_N - Nernst Voltage

ΔG_f - Gibbs free energy formation

R_g - molar gas constant, J/mol K

T_{avg} - Average temperature of fuel cell

F - Faraday constant C/mol

P_{H_2} - Partial pressure of Hydrogen

P_{O_2} - Partial pressure of Oxygen

The ohmic loss in the system is because of the loss of resistance in the electron flow in both cathode and anode. The interconnection losses in the fuel cell due to the ion flow along the electrolytes of the SOFC. The activation losses are corresponding to the starting charge in the system which is used to start the reaction.

3.4.3. Ohmic Losses in Fuel Cell

Ohmic losses in the anode corresponds to the Activation energy, resistivity of the fuel cell,

$$\text{Ohmic_loss_in_anode} = (P_{an} * T_{an}) / A_{act}$$

$$\text{Ohmic_loss_in_Cathode} = (P_{cat} * T_{cat}) / A_{act}$$

$$\text{Ohmic_loss_in_electrode} = (P_{ele} * T_{ele}) / A_{act}$$

P - resistivity_ohm.m

T - electrode_tortuosity

Int - interconnection

A_{act} - constant for activation electrode

This gives the total ohmic losses happen in anode, cathode, electrode and interconnection of the solid oxide fuel cell.

3.4.4. Concentration losses in fuel cell

Concentration losses in the fuel cell is due to the factor of electrode and other constituents retarding the flow of electrons when the syngas is passed through it. Since the concentration losses is happening only in the anode and cathode because the flow of electrons is not happening in the electrolyte and interconnection, hence those are not considered.

$$\text{Loss}_{in_cathode} = (RT/2F) * \ln (1 - (U_f * U_a))$$

$$\text{Loss}_{in_anode} = (RT/4F) * \ln (1 - (U_f * U_a))$$

R- molar gas constant J/mol K

F- Faraday constant C/mol

U_f- Fuel utilization factor

T- Operational temperature

This loss is majorly concerned with the utilization factor air and fuel.

3.4.5. Activation Losses

Activation of the fuel cell in the cell is due to flow of current along the fuel cell when the power is generated. This loss is majorly concerned with the smaller cells compared to the larger ones. At cathode

$$(1/R_{cat} - a) = (2F / R_g T_{op} * K_a * (P_{H2} / P_O) * e^{-(Ea/RgT_{op})}$$

$$\text{Activation_loss_at_cathode} = R_{car} - a * \text{Current_Density}$$

At Anode,

$$(1/R_{an} - a) = (4F/R_g T_{op} * K_a * (P_{O2}/P_O) * e^{-(Ea/RgT_{op})}$$

$$\text{Activation_loss_at_Anode} = R_{an} - a * \text{Current_Density}$$

$$\text{Total_Voltage_in_The_system_will_be} = V_N - \text{Voltage_losses_due_to(Ohmic + Concentration + Activation)}$$

T^{op} – Operational Temperature

E – Activation Energy

Current density j- mA/cm²

3.5. Current Calculation

Fuel cell in Solid Oxide fuel cell is assumed as pile of cells clustered together. The current density of the cell as been assumed 178 mA/cm² and of the active area of the fuel cell used for the utilization is 70m².

Chapter 4

Computational Development

Aspen plus was selected for the simulation of the syn gas utilization system on downstream because of its flexibility and incorporating excel codes. Aspen plus has various utility devices like gas turbine, compressors, heat exchangers, reactor models, splitters, and mixers for simulating different utilization system as flow models. of utilization different streams and also of utilizing the different components for calculation of the utilization.

With use of Aspen plus, feasibility of utilization system can be analyzed on different operational parameters of system. The outcome of the process can be checked for different input parameters which affect the utilization system. Operational parameters can be checked for different operational conditions for optimization and for comparison.

In this utilization system of design model, for the values and properties of syn gas data for Ms. Anne Jayanthi (9) was used.

Syngas Composition					
Component	kmol/hr	Mole % wet basis	Molecular Wt.	mass flow rate (kg/h)	
H ₂	1.13	18.22	2	2.27	
CO	1.01	16.26	28	28.358	
CO ₂	1.18	19.02	44	52.131	
CH ₄	1.09	17.59	16	17.537	
H ₂ O	1.32	21.31	18	23.898	
Char	0.47	7.58	16.06	7.587	

Table 4.1. Syngas Composition

4.1. Utilization system Design

Syn gas utilization system is done by incorporating various aspen models on flow sheet. Different reactor and other utilization components are assigned for different models. Modelling of combustion and heat exchanging devices on the aspen flow sheet gives a different result by varying the inputs to the process. Since the overall system depends on model of combustion of syn gas which generate energy for system.

4. 1. 1 Equipment for Combustion

For process of combustion in combustion chamber RSTOIC reactor of Aspen plus was used. In this system minimum operating pressure is the pressure attained after compression. Combustion takes place in the closed chamber of gas turbine in which the adiabatic temperature has been calculated by the RSTOIC model for complete combustion. In RSTOIC model heat duty of reactor is assumed as Oto calculate the temperature of complete combustion. RSTOIC model majorly cares of the stoichiometric modes of the reaction takes place in the reactor.

For boiler kind of systems RGIBBS rector model is used, which works according to minimum Gibbs energy formation to find out final conditions and composition of the reaction in the model. This gives the system's operating condition for different operational temperatures, pressures, and heat duty of the system.

RYIELD reactor models is used in the system to get defined output of components at exit of reactor for specified input of feedstock or components fed into system. RYIELD will calculate values according to operating conditions set on it. Factors affecting the reactions will be calculated internally and final results are produced.

4.1.2. Turbine and Compressors

Process of compression and expansion for compressor and turbine is done in the COMPR and MCOMPR model of Aspen plus which is used for gas and liquid(steam) streams respectively. Both the streams calculate the change in enthalpy for system power generation. Pressure at inlet and outlet is considered to calculate energy generated from turbine. Back pressure turbine conditions are considered in the process of extracting steam. In compressor model power is required, whereas in the turbine work is getting out form the system.

4.1.3. Heat Exchangers

HEATX model of Aspen plus is used for heat exchanging between two streams. For heat exchanging the main factor to be considered is, outlet temperature of the cold stream is lesser than the inlet temperatures or else the equipment will be bypassed by the simulator engine.

4.1.4. Mixers, Splitters, and Separators

For mixing two different streams in system, MIXER model is used. For this both the streams are to be in same state and temperature is not a constraint. By using the SPLITTER model, defined percentage of component from the input stream can be separated into two streams. Whereas in SSPLIT model of separation which uses the separation of solid-liquid or solid - gas state streams which is considered as centrifugal action of separation.

In solid oxide fuel cell model SEP model is used as anode to separate the gases. Separated gases send to combustion chamber and to anode for thermochemical reaction.

4.2. ASPEN declarations

In the process of simulation other than fixing the model on the flow sheet, operational parameters and other user defined values need to enter in the system for simulating the reaction. This has different conditions, and the values need to enter on three different places namely:

- Properties
- Stream values
- Blocks
- Calculator blocks

And, in this model flue gas from the gasification column is mixed with the gases at exit of the gas turbine which is used to tap more heat from these gases.

4.2.1. Properties

In properties block components which takes place in all models entered which will be appeared as the overall data of components utilized in the stream. Then next, component entered in components block will appear in component blocks. Components need to refer as conventional, non - conventional and solid in component block. For non-conventional heat capacities need to be inserted. Declarations will depend on the type of system that we utilize in the model.

Pure component block has been utilized in the system which will be used to enter the heating values for the non - conventional components take part in the system. These values are not in ASPEN data banks. Hence, we need to enter to set of values for these non-conventional components. Stream class need to be mentioned in the system for an overall definition of streams in the models.

4.3. Simulation of Biomass gasification for syngas production.

Gasification is processed in four zones, which are in following order:

1. Pyrolysis
2. Decomposition
3. Combustion
4. Reduction

Following assumptions are made for the biomass gasification process:

- Process is steady state.
- No pressure drops and no heat loss is considered.
- All components considered are in chemical equilibrium.
- Sulfur, nitrogen and chlorine in biomass are assumed to go to the gas phase.

4.3.1. Data for Feed (Biomass Stream)

Ultimate Analysis (Dry Basis)	
C	42.54 wt.-%
H	6.25 wt.-%
O	38.68 wt.-%
N	0.80 wt.-%
S	0.23 wt.-%
Cl	0.49 wt.-%
Ash	11.01 wt.-%

Proximate Analysis	
Moisture	8.32 wt.-% (moisture included Basis)
Volatiles	70.28 wt.-% (dry basis)
Fixed C	18.71 wt.-% (dry basis)
Ash	11.01 wt.-% (dry basis)

Sulfanal Analysis	
Organic	0.23 wt.-% (dry basis)

- Operating Temperature of 100°C
- Operating Pressure of 1 bar

Aspen Plus Simulation Sheet of Biomass Gasification to Syngas-

Material Result-

Material	Vol.% Curves	Wt. % Curves	Petroleum	Polymers	Solids	Status	MOISTURE	SYNGAS	5	6	2	S1	S2	S11	SYNGAS	SYNGAS
Description																
From			SEP1	SEP2	DECOMPOS	GASIFIER	DRYER						B1	B2	SEP2	SEP2
To				GASIFIER	SEP2	SEP1	B1	B2	GASIFIER							
Stream Class			MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC	MIXCINC
Maximum Relative Error																
Cost Flow	\$/hr															
- Total Stream																
Temperature	C		100	800	800	800	100	25	80	80	800	800	800	800	800	800
Pressure	bar		1	1	1	1	1	1	30	30	1	1	30	30	1	1
Mass Vapor Fraction			0	1	0.973	0.986011	0	0	1	0.998412	1	1	0.998412	1	1	1
Mass Liquid Fraction			1	0	0	0	0.044	1	0	0.00158792	0	0	0.00158792	0	0	0
Mass Solid Fraction			0	0	0.027	0.0139886	0.956	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mass Enthalpy	kJ/kg		-15631.2	-7113.35	32225	-7014.29	-5430.98	-15972.1	-2.96168	-110.345	-7113.35	-7113.35	-7113.35	-7113.35	-7113.35	-7113.35
Mass Density	gm/cc		0.918292	0.000306441	0.000137817	0.000310789	1.29422	0.993957	0.0121974	0.0329398	0.000306441	0.000306441	0.000306441	0.000306441	0.000306441	0.000306441
Enthalpy Flow	kW		-191.047	-3595.02	8557.53	-3595.25	-1508.6	-4436.69	-0.822688	-27.2558	-3595.02	-3595.02	-3595.02	-3595.02	-3595.02	-3595.02
+ Mass Flows	kg/hr		44	1819.41	956	1845.22	1000	1000	1000	889.221	1819.41	1819.41	1819.41	1819.41	1819.41	1819.41
- Mass Fractions																
BIOMASS			0	0	0	0	0.956	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Material	Vol.% Curves	Wt. % Curves	Petroleum	Polymers	Solids	Status	MOISTURE	SYNGAS	5	6	2	S1	S2	S11	SYNGAS	SYNGAS
H2O			1	0.145292	0	0.143259	0.044	1	0.01	0.0112458	0.145292	0.145292	0.145292	0.145292	0.145292	0.145292
H2			0	0.0121749	0.053	0.0120045	0	0	0.110779	0	0.0121749	0.0121749	0.0121749	0.0121749	0.0121749	0.0121749
CO			0	0.255264	0	0.251694	0	0	0	0	0.255264	0.255264	0.255264	0.255264	0.255264	0.255264
CO2			0	0.586752	0	0.578544	0	0	0	0	0.586752	0.586752	0.586752	0.586752	0.586752	0.586752
CH4			0	1.75563e-05	0	1.73107e-05	0	0	0	0	1.75563e-05	1.75563e-05	1.75563e-05	1.75563e-05	1.75563e-05	1.75563e-05
NH3			0	1.11371e-07	0	1.09813e-07	0	0	0	0	1.11371e-07	1.11371e-07	1.11371e-07	1.11371e-07	1.11371e-07	1.11371e-07
H2S			0	0.000446783	0	0.000440533	0	0	0	0	0.000446783	0.000446783	0.000446783	0.000446783	0.000446783	0.000446783
ASH			0	0	0.027	0.0139886	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MEOH			0	1.00368e-10	0	9.89644e-11	0	0	0	0	1.00368e-10	1.00368e-10	1.00368e-10	1.00368e-10	1.00368e-10	1.00368e-10
N2			0	5.24529e-05	0.0001	5.17192e-05	0	0	0	0	5.24529e-05	5.24529e-05	5.24529e-05	5.24529e-05	5.24529e-05	5.24529e-05
O2			0	0	0.406	9.2626e-19	0	0	0.879221	0.988754	0	0	0	0	0	0
S			0	0	0.0008	1.51719e-12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
C			0	0	0.5131	1.97121e-29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Volume Flow	l/min															
- MIXED Substream																
Phase			Liquid Phase	Vapor Phase	Vapor Phase	Vapor Phase	Liquid Phase	Liquid Phase	Vapor Phase		Vapor Phase	Vapor Phase				
Temperature	C		100	800	800	800	100	25	80	80	800	800	800	800	800	800
Pressure	bar		1	1	1	1	1	1	30	30	1	1	30	30	1	1

4.4. Continuous heat and Power Model

In the continuous heat and power flow model gas turbine is modelled using COMPR FROM Aspen Plus as the model of the compressor. For combustion chamber RSTOIC from Aspen Plus is used, which is used for the combustion of syngas with the compressed air from compressor. Combustion model in the RSTOIC will give the adiabatic flame temperature of the combustion in gases. To maintain the temperature inlet to the gas turbine at 1500°C additional compressed air is sent to the gas turbine. A pressure ratio of 9 is maintained in the compressor and the turbine has been expanded to its lower operational pressure for the extraction of heat from the flue gas.

In the model, heat exchangers are used in exchanging heat from flue gas for waste heat recovery. Heat is exchanged from flue gas using waste heat recovery steam generator and air heater for utilization system. Heat is trapped by both equipment for gasification process heating.

4.5. Combined Cycle Gas Turbine

In this process the gas turbine is modelled similar to the continuous heat and power model. But the pressure at exit will increase from previous mode. Because of the need to utilize heat from flue gas to generate from steam turbine with process heat generation. Like the above model heat the heat recovery equipment like heat recovery steam generator and the air heater system has been utilized which will decrease the temperature of the flue gas at exit.

The exit gases from the utilization system have been maintained at 105°C to prevent the condensation of gases and to provide the energy to gases for exhaust from the system. The temperature at the exit of the pre-heater system is around 100°C and the heat recovery system is 400°C with an increase of 150°C super heat at super heater. The steam is then expanded in the steam turbine to generate process steam at 5 bar and 350°C at the exit of the steam turbine 1 and then remaining is expanded in the second steam turbine to generate maximum power. Pressure at 40 bar is selected for operation of turbine.

SSPLIT is introduced in the system to separate the feedstock and flue gas mixture from the input stream which has mixture of flue gas and bagasse after drying.

Drying is done through RYIELD reactor which yield the product specified by the user for the conditions required by the user at an operating condition required by the user at an operating condition and gives the output of heat or the process needed by the system at exit.

4.6. Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Model

The Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Model of power generation system is done through incorporating Microsoft excel for its calculation of power through fuel cell. Since its a bottoming cycle of power generation system exhaust from the fuel cell can be allowed to expand through gas turbines which will produce additional power.

Compressors are used for compressing both syngas and air to increase the temperature of both streams which bring temperature of streams nearer to point of combustion in system. RGIBBS model of reactor is used in the process of pre-forming and on the reaction in anode. This reactor utilizes the minimum Gibbs energy formation of component at a temperature. In Pre-Former and anode blocks certain components are assumed as inert. Because the reaction happen by these components will affect the system temperature and the operation of fuel cell.

Chapter 5

Results and Declaration

5.1. Utilization System

Syn gas utilization system comprises of Gas turbine, Gas engine and solid oxide fuel cell model. Gas has been combusted in the combustion chamber of gas turbine. The gases then expand in the gas turbine. In gas engine syn gas is combusted at the end of compression stroke. Adiabatic flame temperature of about 1900° C is reached in the combustion chamber. Hence more air is required for cooling. Additional air supplied for maintaining temperature of inlet at gas turbine. This will increase the auxiliary energy required by utilization system for compressing additional air. This factor is not considered in gas engine systems.

Inter - cooling is not provided in current systems due to increased flow rate air to cool the gas on inlet to the gas turbine. Gas expanded in the turbine is mixed with the flue gas from gasifier to utilize the waste heat from gasifier. Exhaust of the flue gases has maintained below 105° C for considering the factor of condensation of flue gases. Power produced by the gas turbine is uniform and non-variable. But using secondary heat recovery system will change the efficiency of system. Overall analysis of the gasification utilization proves that this system can provide the energy with process heat recovery without use of any energy aid. This doesn't affect energy utilization efficiency to a larger extent.

Process heat recovery system generates heat for heat required by gasification reaction. Steam at a rate of 61 kg/hr. with a pressure of 5 bar at 350° C was generated to fulfil the needs of gasification reaction in the BFB column. Hot air at a rate of 109 kg/hr. with a pressure of 5 bar 300° C has been generated for the combustion column of gasifier.

5.1.1. Electrical conversion efficiency

Electrical conversion efficiency of syn gas utilization system is around 30-40%. Depending on the process heat application needed by the system efficiency will vary. Whereas SOFC model of power generation produces higher power due to additional energy generation by fuel cell.

5.2. Continuous Heat and Power system

Hot gas from combustion chamber is expanded in gas turbine which produces electrical energy directly. Thermal energy conversion takes place by passing flue gas through air heater and processing hot steam generator. In this model of utilization energy produced is higher than other systems. Due to reducing the gas pressure beyond 2 bars, it produces higher energy in flue gas. Heat loss in CHP system was analyzed by using heat recovery systems for tapping it. This gives an idea about the energy that can be generated by passing the flue gas on through the waste heat recovery equipments for higher energy tapping.

Stream Name	AIR	COMPAIR	AIR2CC	SYNGAS	CCEXHA	2GT	GTEXHA	FLUEGAS	2PROCESS	TOPROCESS	HRSG2AIR	TOCOLUMN	EXHAUST
TO	COMP	AIRSPPLIT	CC	CC	COOLER	GT	MIXER	MIXER	HRSG		AIRHEAT		
FROM		COMPAIR	AIRSPPLIT		CC	COOLER	GTEXHA		MIXER	HRSG	HRSG2AIR	AIRHEAT	AIRHEAT
PHASE	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR
SUBSTREAM: MIXED													
MOLE FLOW kmol/hr													
H2	0	0	0	1.15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CO	0	0	0	1.02	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CO2	0	0	0	1.2	3.29	3.29	3.29	0.24	3.54	0	3.54	0	3.54
CH4	0	0	0	1.08	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H2O	0	0	0	1.34	4.64	4.64	4.64	0	4.64	6.66	4.64	0	4.64
N2	20.54	20.54	13.69	0	13.69	20.54	20.54	1.31	21.84	0	21.84	4.11	21.84
O2	5.46	5.46	3.64	0	0.4	2	2	0.08	2.3	0	2.3	1.09	2.3
TOTAL FLOW kmol/hr	26	26	17.33	5.78	22.03	30.7	30.7	1.63	32.33	6.66	32.33	5.2	32.33
TOTAL FLOW kg/hr	750	750	500	125	625	875	875	50	925	120	925	150	925
TEMPERATURE C	30	294.77	294.77	400	1955.88	1563.36	805.61	950	812.89	400	486.57	300	449.02
PRESSURE BAR	3	15	15	5	27	45	2	1	1	5	1	5	1
ENERGY BALANCE													
ENERGY IN H2	0	0	0	15464.56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ENERGY IN CO	0	0	0	14922.35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ENERGY IN CO2	0	0	0	28417.03	339181.64	247675.5	132504.7	10001.77	123861.6	0	62186.18	0	55490.73
ENERGY IN CH4	0	0	0	32597.18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ENERGY IN H2O	0	0	0	0	373174.97	271696.34	142542.27	0	124033.42	345958.8	63420.32	0	56845.35
ENERGY IN N2	3187.52	170988.43	106867.78	0	844338.1	944126.13	549298.26	33349.64	509834.85	0	266871.67	32705.63	239847.71
ENERGY IN O2	854	4732.78	29520.49	0	26242.46	108002.97	69096.79	2205.95	62470.53	0	32537.85	9038.18	29200.2
TOTAL ENERGY KJ/hr	4041.52	218221.21	136388.27	91401.11	158293.17	1571500.94	893442.02	45557.35	820200.4	345958.8	42501.02	41743.81	381384.2
TOTAL ENERGY KW	1.12	60.62	37.89	25.39	439.7	436.53	248.18	12.65	227.83	96.1	118.06	11.6	105.94

Table 5.1. Continuous Heat and Power System Data

The energy generated by the gas turbine is 215 KW as there is very little need for end heat utilization, such as other than steam generation and process air heating. Heat duty of waste heat recovery systems are less as it is handling little amount of cold fluid in the system. Utility systems like process heat generation system and air heating system have been utilized to recover the maximum heat. Since minimal heat is tapped in this system, heat carried away by the flue gas is more.

Input Energy		
Component	KW	%
Heat Input through fuel	439.04	81.48
Sensible heat in the fuel	25.39	4.71
Heat input through air	1.12	0.21
Sensible heat through air	60.62	11.25
Heat input through flue gas	12.65	2.35
Heat input to gasification air	0.21	0.04
Total Input Energy	538.82	100
Output Energy		
Component	KW	%
Work done by the gas turbine	200.52	37.21
Work needed by the compressor	45.34	8.41
Heat taken away by exhaust flue gases	105.94	19.66
Heat taken away by exhaust steam	96.10	17.84
Heat duty of the HRSG	55.22	10.25
Heat duty of the air heater	10.56	1.96
Heat carried away by the gasification air	11.60	2.15
Losses	13.55	2.51
Total output energy	538.82	100.00

5.1.1. Influence of Compression ratio on the system

Compression ratio increases the energy availability and the auxiliary energy usage by compressor which may become one third of the systems. At compression ratio of 5 the power needed by the compressor is around 25 30 KW with losses. But with the increase of the compression ratio to 9 the energy needed by the compressor becomes 65 KW with losses. This also increases the operational pressures of combustion chamber. This will increase the energy produced by the system.

5.2. Combined Cycle Gas Turbine

Exhaust from the gas turbine is allowed to recover heat by various heat transfer equipments. By reducing the moisture content in the fuel, the gasification process will get more efficient. The dryer in this system is utilizing heat from exhaust flue gases from pre - heater. The moisture content of the feedstock is converted into water vapor utilizing heat from flue gas. The feed stock and flue gas are separated by cyclone separator as individual streams.

Energy of 44 KW is needed by dryer for drying of biomass feedstock. The flue gas and the fuel mixture are then mixed in the reactor to exchange the heat between two streams. The outlet temperature of the flue gas has been around 150° C. The flue gases and the dried fuel have been separated by the cyclone separator which works according to the centrifugal force of separation. Due to the process of drying, the energy generation through the steam turbine is reduced. This is due to the factor of maintaining energy in flue gases to maximum for drying. Waste heat energy utilization system's flow rate is reduced to maintain the temperature of flue gases for drying.

Stream name	AIR	COMPAIR	SYNGAS	CCEXHA	2GT	GTEXHA	FLUEGAS	2SH	HRSG2SH	AIRH2PRE	WATER	2PREHEAT	EXHAUST	TOST	CONDENSA
To	COMP	AIRSPLIT	CC	COOLER	GT	MIXER	MIXER	SH	SH	PREHEAT	B13	PREHEAT		ST	
From		COMP		cc	COOLER	GT		MIXER	HRSG	AIRHEAT		B13	PREHEAT	SH	ST2
Phase	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	LIQUID	LIQUID	VAPOR	VAPOR	LIQUID
Substream: MIXED															
Mole Flow kmol/hr															
H2	0	0	1.15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
co	0	0	1.02	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CO2	0	0	1.2	3.29	3.29	3.29	0.24	3.54	0	3.54	0	0	3.54	0	0
CH4	0	0	1.08	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H2O	0	0	1.34	4.64	4.64	4.64	0	4.64	11.1	4.64	11.1	11.1	4.64	11.1	7.72
N2	21.91	21.91	0	13.69	21.91	21.91	1.31	23.21	0	23.21	0	0	23.21	0	0
O2	5.82	5.82	0	0.4	2.58	2.58	0.08	2.57	0	2.67	0	0	2.67	0	0
Total Flow kmol/hr	27.73	27.73	5.78	22.03	32.43	32.43	1.53	34.06	11.1	34.06	11.1	11.1	34.06	11.1	7.72
Total Flow kg/hr	800	800	125	625	925	925	50	975	200	975	200	200	975	200	139
Temperature C	30	294.77	400	1955.88	1506.45	906.3	950	908.38	400	444.85	30	34.29	396.97	283.6	55
Pressure bar	3	15	5	27	45	5	1	1	5	1	1	50	1	3	0.8
ENERGY BALANCE															
Energy In H2	0	0	15464.56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Energy In CO	0	0	14922.35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Energy In CO2	0	0	28417.03	639181.64	47675.50	1132504.7	10001.77	1	0	27537.37	0	0	18341.68	0	0
Energy In CH4	0	0	32597.18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Energy In H2O	0	0	0	3.73E+05	2.72E+05	1.43E+05	0.00E+00	1.43E+05	5.83E+05	2.90E+04	2.51E+04	2.51E+04	1.96E+04	6.20E+05	23702.28
Energy In N2	8.19E+03	1.71E+05	0.00E+00	8.44E+05	6.29E+05	5.49E+05	3.33E+04	5.84E+05	0.00E+00	1.24E+05	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	8.38E+04	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Energy In O2	8.54E+02	4.72E+04	0.00E+00	2.62E+04	1.95E+04	6.91E+04	2.21E+03	7.15E+04	0.00E+00	1.49E+04	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	1.01E+04	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Total Energy in KJ/hr	4.04E+03	2.18E+05	9.14E+04	1.58E+06	1.17E+06	8.93E+05	1.46E+05	9.41E+05	6.83E+05	1.95E+05	2.51E+04	2.51E+04	1.32E+05	6.20E+05	2.37E+04
Total Energy in KW	1.12	60.62	25.39	439.7	324.51	248.18	12.65	261.36	162.04	54.23	6.99	6.96	36.62	172.23	6.58

Table 5.2. CCGT Data

The energy generated is around 183 KW whereas the total energy generated by the gas and steam turbine is around 205 KW. Energy utilized by the compressor is around 113 KW.

The heat duty by various equipments has been reduced by about 10% due to the reduced flow rate in the waste heat energy utilization systems. The heat duty of the dryer to reduce moisture content is about 44 KW.

Input Energy		
Component	KW	%
Heat input through fuel	439.04	81.48
Sensible heat in the fuel	25.39	4.71
Heat input through air	1.12	0.21
Sensible heat through air	60.62	11.25
Heat input through flue gas	12.65	2.35
Heat input to gasification air	0.22	0.04
Total Input Energy	538.82	100
Output Energy		
Component	KW	%
Work done by the gas turbine	182.96	33.96
Work done by the steam turbine	25.32	4.70
Work needed by the compressor	42.53	7.89
Heat taken away by exhaust flue gases	13.34	2.48
Heat taken away by exhaust steam	42.56	7.90
Heat taken away by steam condensate	5.64	1.05
Heat duty of the superheater	10.23	1.90
Heat duty of the HRSG	135.26	25.10
Heat duty of the air heater	10.56	1.96
Heat duty of water preheater	8.27	1.53
Heat carried away by the gasification air	11.60	2.15
Work done by pump	0.93	0.17
Heat duty of dryer	44.71	8.30
Losses	4.92	0.91
Total output energy	538.82	100.00

5.2.1 Influence of flue gas temperature on the system

Final gas temperature plays an important role for the energy available and utilization of the gases in the drying system. The main problem in the process of drying is burning of fuel during the exchange of heat between flue gas and the fuel feed stock to be dried. When the gas temperature is low the fuel system needs extra heat to run the process. As far as the present system is concerned the final temperature is huge and thus a more amount of heat can be utilized. Hence less external heat is needed.

5.2.2. Influence of drying

With the decrease in the moisture content needed at exit of dryer heat duty of dryer get increased. More heat from flue gas has been trapped by feed stock for the reduction of moisture content. Hence the energy losses through exhaust flue gas are also reduced.

Moisture Content (Final)	15	20	25
Heat duty of dryer	44.71	30.41	16.12

5.3. Solid Oxide Fuel Cell System

In solid oxide fuel cells, energy is generated by solid oxide fuel cells. Then the combusted gas in the solid oxide fuel cell is expanded in the gas turbine. Gas turbine with fuel cell produces higher efficiency than the steam turbine which produces energy of about 125 KW. But Solid oxide fuel cell produces a power of around 83 KW with expansion in gas turbine makes the best option for other models of syn gas utilization. Cooling air requirement is reduced in this system. The energy conversion from DC to AC plays has a efficiency is around 98%, hence more power is available from the system.

Stream Name	SYNGAS	COMP GAS	MIXED GAS	2PREFORM	PRE2ANOD	ANOD2SPL	CAT2CC	CCEX	AIR	CAT2ANOD	CCEX	2GT	HX2HX	HX2AIRH	2PREFORM	AIRH2PR0	H2OGASIF	EXHAUST	
TO	GASCOM	MIXER	PREFORM	IDREFORM	ANODE	SPLITTER	CC	GASMIX	AIRCOMP	ANODE	GASMIX	GT	HX	AIRHEAT	PREFORM	PROCESS	PROCESS	PROCESS	
FROM	GASCOM	MIXER	HX	PREFORM	ANODE	CATHODE	CC			CATHODE	CC	GASMIX	HX2	HX	HX	AIRHEAT		PROCESS	
hase	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	VAPOR	LIQUID	VAPOR
Substream: MIXED																			
Mole Flow kmol/hr																			
H2	1.15	1.15	1.15	0	3.44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CO	1.02	1.02	1.62	0	2.38	2.3-8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CO2	1.2	1.2	1.59	0	1.59	1.5-9	0	3.29	0	0	3.29	3.29	3.29	3.29	0	3.29	0	3.29	
CH4	1.08	1.08	1.18	0	0.42	0.4-2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H2O	1.34	1.34	3.42	2.22	4.88	8.31	0	6.86	0	0	6.86	6.86	6.86	6.86	2.22	6.86	4.44	6.86	
N2	0	0	2.17	0	2.17	8.67	6.5	13.01	15.06	6.5	13.01	15.06	15.06	15.06	0	15.06	0	15.06	
O2	0	0	0	0	0	0.01	1.73	0.22	4	1.73	0.22	0.77	0.77	0.77	0	0.77	0	0.77	
Total Flow kmol/hr	5.78	5.78	11.13	2.22	14.88	21.39	8.23	23.39	19.06	8.23	23.39	25.99	25.99	25.99	2.22	25.99	4.44	25.99	
Total Flow kg/hr	12.5.00	125	259.17	40	299.17	536.67	237.5	640	550.00	237.5	640	715	715	715	40	715	80	715	
Temperature C	400	778.07	831.36	500	470.76	900	613.83	1591.78	30	613.83	1591.78	1482.78	635.98	493.52	500	450.42.	30	173.38	
Pressure bar	5	50	5	5	5	5	25	25	5	25	25	25	2	2	5	2	5	2	
ENERGY BALANCE																			
Energy in H2	15464.56	12948.3	14810.73	0	36813.25	0.02	0	63.12	0	0	63.12	57.98	29.85	21.26	0	13.75	0	2.7	
Energy in CO	14922.35	12447.68	14278.33	0	26399.69	59965.1	0	130.55	0	0	130.55	120.67	61.75	43.4	0	27.7	0	5.35	
Energy in CO2	28417.03	23661.1	27179.2	0	26788.98	63518.19	0	265097.18	0	0	265097.18	243078.28	129979.3	89792.94	0	55827.28	0	10049.03	
Energy in CH4	3297.18	26742.52	31060.25	0	7689.55	20264.82	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Energy in H2O	0	0	58395.24	120129.6	63692.61	252934.1	0	430050.26	0	0	430050.26	193625.36	192458.3	133574.3	120129.6	84367.08	270564	16050.05	
Energy in N2	0	0	29872.76	0	23812.09	215774.7	115893.3	633278.6	2191.42	115893.3	633278.6	677453.8	346725.01	243917.5	0	155948.5	0	30240.5	
Energy in O2	0	0	5051	0	39.8	362.5	32521.94	11338.04	5-87.13	32521.94	11338.04	36464.86	18752.55	13173.74	0	ssn.s2	0	1593.92	
Total Energy in KJ/hr	1401.11	75799.61	175647.01	120129.6	185235.97	612819.74	148415.32	1339957.74	2778.55	148415.32	1339957.74	1350800.94	688006.83	480523.19	120129.6	304562.01	270564	57941.54	
Total Energy in KW	25.39	21.06	48.79	33.37	51.45	170.23	41.23	372.21	0.77	41.23	372.21	375.22	191.11	133.48	33.37	84.6	75.16	16.09	

Table 5.3. Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Data

The energy generated by the gas turbine is around 168 KW and the energy produced through the solid oxide fuel cell is around 83 KW. Most of the flue gas heat is utilized in the process of preforming water and in process of heating air for anode. The increase in the temperature of about 300° C produces the power in the gas turbine of about 150 KW and in the solid oxide fuel cell of about 50 KW. Hence more heat is added in the system for producing a better conversion in anode.

Input Energy		
Component	KW	%
Heat input through fuel	439.04	86.44
Sensible heat in the fuel	25.39	5.00
Heat input through air	1.12	0.22
Sensible heat through air	29.51	5.81
Heat input through flue gas	12.65	2.49
Heat input to gasification air	0.22	0.042
Total Input Energy	507.93	100
Output Energy		
Component	KW	%
Work done by the gas turbine	168.76	33.23
Work done by the SOFC	83.00	16.34
Work needed by the compressors	43.67	8.60
Heat taken away by exhaust flue gases	16.09	3.17
Heat taken away by process steam	41.87	8.24
Heat duty of the heat exchangers	78.26	15.41
Heat duty of the air heater	11.09	2.18
Heat duty of the water heater	57.67	11.35
Losses	7.52	1.48
Total output energy	507.93	100.00

5.3.1. Power from Fuel Cell

Power produced in fuel cell is depends on the operating temperatures of fuel cell. In this system the operational voltage depends on various factors. Fuel cell molar concentration is actively taking part in the cell reaction with the increase in pressures and temperatures of the cell. Fuel cell voltage has been stated as the Nernst voltage which has been accounted with different losses like ohmic losses, Activation losses and Concentration losses of the fuel cell.

Voltage generated in fuel cell will change considerably with a change in utilization factor of the fuel cell. The fuel cell systems shows an decrease in the voltage of the systems when the utilization factor of the system get decreased.

Parameters	Values	Units
Nernst Voltage	0.9117401	V
Total ohmic losses	0.037999	V
Total concentration losses	0.039951	V
Total activation losses	0.182	V
Net voltage in the system	0.7316921	V
Current density	178	mA/sq.cm
Power in the system	83.34	KW

5.3.2. Influence of Temperature increase in Pre-forming and Air heating

With the increase in pre-forming temperatures conversion at the pre-former get increased. Energy produced through gas turbines increases with a reduction of exhaust flue gas temperatures. Increase of air heating temperatures doesn't affect energy produced through gas turbine to a larger extent. Exhaust flue gas temperatures also decrease. At the exit of anode the composition of CO gets increased at little fraction

- **Influence of pre-forming**

Temperature C	400	450	500
Power in gas turbine	162.35	165.32	168.77
Pressure at Anode in bar	5	5	5
Composition of gases at Anode			
H2	4.76E-07	6.11E-07	1.05E-06
CO	2.35	2.36	2.38
CO2	1.59	1.59	1.59
CH4	0.45	0.44	0.42
H2O	8.25	8.28	8.31
N2	8.67	8.67	8.67
O2	0.07	0.04	0.01
Total flow kmol/hr.	21.38	21.35	21.39
Total flow kg/hr.	536.67	536.67	536.67
Exhaust flue gas Temperature	225.34	200.35	181.72

- Effect of Air Heating

Temperatures C	350	400	450
Power in gas turbine	167.52	168.77	169.99
Composition of gas in the after anode			
H2	1.02E-06	1.05E-06	1.02E-06
co	2.37	2.38	2.38
CO2	1.59	1.59	1.59
CH4	0.41	0.42	0.42
H2O	8.31	8.31	8.31
N2	8.67	8.67	8.67
O2	0.014519	0.01	0.01
Total Flow kmol/hr	21.39	21.39	21.39
Total Flow kg/hr	536.66	536.67	536.67
Exhaust flue gas temperatures C	201.83	181.72	172

5.3.3. Influence of Anode temperature

Energy produced through fuel cells will increase with the increase of temperature. This is due to an increase in the voltage generated on the system. Power produced by gas turbines increases because of products to the combustion chamber inlet to the system at higher temperatures.

5.3.4. Influence of Heat Recovery

Since more heat is trapped by the pre-forming steam and with the air heating, heat available for the gasification column and for combustion column get reduced. This pushes the factor of not utilizing steam turbine for energy generation.

5.4. Comparison

Various systems have been compared and assessed here. At present gas turbine models are being widely used now in various cycles as the systems with practical due to its feasibility and easy operation, easy starting and easy adaptable to different conditions.

As far as the solid oxide fuel models are concerned the operational parameters are very similar to the gas turbine models, whereas the cost has been higher than other models due to fact that the fuel cell electrolytes of higher cost.

Parameters	CHP	CCGT	SOFC
Total Input	538.82	538.82	507.93
Output on GT	200.52	182.96	168.76
Output on ST	-	20.32	-
Fuel Cell Energy	-	-	83
Electrical Efficiency	37.21	37.69	49.57
Compressor Work	45.34	42.53	43.67
Flue gas heat	105.94	13.34	16.52

5.4.1. Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Comparison

Solid oxide fuel cells have been compared with one of the literatures for justification of calculation. In the system we are comparing, they use natural gas for power generation through fuel cell. Due to this higher flow rate of methane, more current is generated in the fuel cell makes the energy generation more suitable in the system. Comparatively higher losses have been considered in the system for DC to AC conversion. As in literature [4], the DC to AC conversion efficiency is 92 %, but in present, DC to AC conversion efficiency is 98%.

Because of the higher current density in the literature model [4], it produces more energy through fuel cells which increases energy generation through fuel cells. Since the current density is more than present model, energy generation through fuel cell is reduced in aspen plus simulated model.

Factors	Literature [4]	Model
Voltage	0.661	0.74
Current density mA/cm ²	200.62	178
Power on fuel cell	87	83
Overall efficiency of the system	49.8	49.57

Chapter 6

Conclusion

By considering various models for syn gas utilization systems with their application of recovering heat from flue gas, each system has its own advantage. Currently most of the biomass energy conversion systems employ combustion models of energy conversion, which operate under a very low efficiency. Losses in combustion are higher than the other process due to the higher moisture content in the biomass feedstock.

Steam and condensate exit from utilization system accounts for higher losses in all systems. These factors make the system much more complicated and costlier on a smaller scale.

Solid oxide produces higher efficiency than other systems. It produces higher efficiency because of higher energy produced by fuel cell and gas turbine by using bottoming cycle. But in gas turbine models the energy produced in the system is majorly related to the compression ratio. In gas turbine model compression ratio increases temperature of combustion chamber. Hence the amount of air inlet onto the system increased. Whereas in gas engine systems the change in compression ratio decreases the incomplete combustion in system.

The efficiency of gas turbine system is much higher. As far as the gas turbine system is considered major cost covers up for the cost of the combustion and utilization module. Similarly for gas turbine systems, more clean gas is needed for combustion in gas turbines. This makes the cost higher for incorporating gas cleaning systems on the utilization side. With the use of fuel cells more clean gas is produced and the cost of the system gets higher.

These factors make the system much more complicated and costlier on a smaller scale. But at larger cycle factor of size to capacity is lesser and hence it can be utilized in larger scale easily.

6.1. Scope of future work

Heat loss optimization study can be studied for reducing the losses in the system. With the change in the operational parameters for different kinds of feedstock can be analyzed. This extends to find out the best operational model of gasification for the energy generation process.

The drying concept can be utilized in the system which will produce an optimization of efficiency and a higher thermodynamics efficiency of the utilization.

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